

Preliminary Results of Angle-Resolved BTDF Characterization of Optical Transmissive Diffusers

Jinglin Fu¹, Jeppe R. Frisvad², Michael Esslinger¹, Tatjana Quast¹ and Alfred Schirmacher¹

¹ *Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Bundesallee 100, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany*

² *Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, Technical University of Denmark, Richard Petersens Plads, Building 324, 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark*

Abstract

Optical diffusers are used in many application areas related to illumination. With the purpose of characterizing the transmission properties of optical diffusers, we present preliminary results of BTDF (Bidirectional Transmittance Distribution Function) measurement with high angular resolution at two different wavelengths. The expanded total uncertainty of the measurement is estimated to be 0.5% in the best case. In this way, the scattering distribution of optical diffusers could be quantitatively described by their BTDF values with high precision, good repeatability and reproducibility. The diffusers' angle-dependent spectral transmittances in the VIS (from 380 nm to 780 nm in the electromagnetic spectrum) are also measured using a commercially available spectrophotometer. Results are compared to simulation calculated from a simple model and a first-step explanation for the sample spectral dependency is proposed.

Keywords

Optical Diffuser, Diffuse Transmission, BTDF, Angle-resolved Detection, Wavelength Dependency

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EMAIL: jinglin.fu@ptb.de (A. 1); jerf@dtu.dk (A. 2); michael.esslinger@ptb.de (A. 3); tatjana.quast@ptb.de (A. 4); alfred.schirmacher@ptb.de (A. 5)

ORCID: 0000-0001-8260-8017 (A. 1); 0000-0002-0603-3669 (A. 2); 0000-0002-2228-7853 (A. 5)

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